

Index of training material

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
nfc_core_Schedule	Information (PDF)	Schedule for the workshop providing a breakdown of topics and timings	Included in this Zenodo record
Tutorial page	Online tutorial (webpage)	Online tutorial on which this workshop is based. Tutorial theory, exercises and examples.	Available via https://sydney-informatics-hub.github.io/customising-nfc_core-workshop/
nfc_core_Q_and_A	Information (PDF)	Archive of questions and their answers from the workshop Slack Channel.	Included in this Zenodo record